

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain
interplaY

Introduction to the benefits of participating in HEREDITARY Task 3.6

26.11.2025

Marcos Casado Barbero, EMBL-EBI

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101137074. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Executive Summary

One of the HEREDITARY project's aims is to **enhance the usability and impact of data** generated and collected within the consortium by ensuring that they adhere to the [FAIR principles](#) — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

By collaborating with the project's data contributors, we will demonstrate how applying FAIRification workflows not only strengthens compliance with **international guidelines** (e.g., 1+MG, ¹ GA4GH) ² but also improves data discoverability and fosters cross-domain research, one of the focal points of this multimodal project.

The process of FAIRification can benefit **(meta)data collected** within the HEREDITARY project, but also **reused data** obtained from other resources (e.g., EGA) and even **synthetic data**.

Task 3.6 (*FAIRification workflows and 1+MG guidelines compliance*) will work in close collaboration with other project tasks that overlap on these goals, WP3 ³ in particular.

As HEREDITARY has already allocated resources to these efforts in this task (lead: EMBL-EBI; partners: UNIPD, ONTO, KUL, CRG, CNAG), **participating data owners can benefit from expert guidance, established frameworks, and tangible improvements** to their datasets at no additional cost.

Below you can find our initial proposal for FAIRification steps that could be implemented using these data resources, including:

1. [Metadata enhancement](#)
2. [Federated Metadata Integration](#)
3. [Linking to Established Standards and Frameworks](#)
4. [Data Use and Sharing Policies](#)
5. [Long-Term Sustainability and Reusability](#)

¹ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

² <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

³

https://hereditary.dei.unipd.it/wiki/doku.php?id=tasks:tasks#wp3_-_multimodal_semantic_integration_platform

Document information

Document Title	Introduction to benefits of Participating with HEREDITARY Task 3.6
Work Package	WP3
Task	3.6
Lead Partner	EMBL
Due date	NA
Date of submission	06.12.2024
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public

Authors

Name	Organisation
Marcos Casado Barbero ⁴	EMBL-EBI ⁵

Revision history

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
v1.1.0	26.11.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Format document as D3.6 annex
v1.0.0	06.12.2024	Marcos Casado Barbero	Create document

⁴ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7747-6256>

⁵ <https://ror.org/02cats52>

Contents

Executive Summary	2
Glossary	5
1. Benefits	6
1.1. Metadata enhancement.....	6
1.2. Federated Metadata Integration.....	7
1.3. Linking to Established Standards and Frameworks.....	7
1.4. Data Use and Sharing Policies.....	8
1.5. Long-Term Sustainability and Reusability.....	9
How can the Task 3.6 team support your work?	9
References	10

Glossary

Abbreviation	Description
1+MG	1+ Million Genomes
CNAG	Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
DCAT-AP	DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary) Application Profile
DUO	Data Use Ontology
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory – European Bioinformatics Institute
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FEGA	Federated European Genome-phenome Archive
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDI	Genome Data Infrastructure
GO	Gene Ontology
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
KUL	KU Leuven (Katholieke Universiteit Leuven)
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
ONTO	Ontotext AD
RUMC	Radboud University Medical Centre
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova
UNITO	Università degli Studi di Torino
WP3	Work Package 3

1. Benefits

1.1. Metadata enhancement

Implement **standardised metadata schemas** (compatible with, e.g., DCAT-AP,⁶ Beacon v2,⁷ Phenopackets,⁸ GDI)⁹ and **controlled vocabularies** (e.g., EFO)¹⁰ to enable richer, more meaningful data descriptions. The Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA) is developing improved metadata standards for human metadata across Europe, and as a data contributor to the project you can benefit from their expertise and continuous effort to meet these standards.

Service logos obtained from their respective homepages.

Furthermore, we can provide improved **context and discoverability** for datasets, even if full data access is restricted. Making a dataset easier to find does not imply it is publicly accessible.

Example

A gut microbiome dataset produced by RUMC can be annotated with DCAT-AP properties to define its origin, modality, and key variables. By incorporating DataCite references and domain ontologies like EFO or HPO, the metadata will guide researchers to understand the dataset's clinical context and improve their ability to identify similar resources across HEREDITARY's data ecosystem.

⁶ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/>

⁷ <https://genomebeacons.org/>

⁸ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/phenopackets/>

⁹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>

1.2. Federated Metadata Integration

Given the importance of federated analysis and learning of the project, it is key to be able to **harmonise metadata across different institutions**. This can be done by aligning datasets with European standards. It may involve improving the way metadata is collected, or mapping the metadata each institution has to a common language (i.e., model), similar to the FEGA efforts.

Icons made by Freepik, obtained from Flaticon

Once participating institutions use the same language (i.e., format their metadata), effective comparisons and analyses can be performed in a federated manner.

Example

Genomic datasets derived from UNIPD and UNITO can be mapped to, for example, FEGA's metadata model, with a rich metadata profile, aligned to Beacon v2. This approach allows for the comparison of metadata across different institutions. Furthermore, it ensures that other HEREDITARY partners can find and request access (if applicable) through federated queries, enabling inter-institutional collaboration while respecting local data governance rules.

1.3. Linking to Established Standards and Frameworks

The goal is for metadata to be **interoperable** not just **within HEREDITARY**, but also **with other European projects**, ensuring compliance with field standards. For this purpose, it is crucial to adopt well-known ontologies (e.g., EFO,¹¹ HPO,¹² GO)¹³ and adhere to guidelines (e.g., GA4GH,¹⁴ 1+MG)¹⁵ for consistent representation of clinical and genomic data elements.

¹¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>

¹² <https://hpo.jax.org/>

¹³ <https://geneontology.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

¹⁵ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

Icons made by Freepik, obtained from Flaticon. OLS logo obtained from OLS. ¹⁶

This may involve creating data dictionaries aligned with these standards, or improving the vocabularies used at source within the project.

Example

An MRI dataset from UNIPD, when annotated with SNOMED CT¹⁷ for imaging features and GA4GH standards for (possible) genomic variants, can be easily aligned with complementary datasets from UNITO or external references like the UK Biobank. This linkage simplifies cross-domain analyses and harmonisation efforts.

1.4. Data Use and Sharing Policies

Integrate **Data Use Ontology** (DUO) ¹⁸ annotations for datasets within HEREDITARY to clarify **access conditions** and align with global data governance frameworks.

Image taken from the DUO documentation. ¹⁹

¹⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/logo.svg>

¹⁷ <https://www.snomed.org/what-is-snomed-ct>

¹⁸ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/data-use-ontology-duo/>

¹⁹ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/data-use-ontology-duo/>

With the addition of well-defined data usage codes, we would allow a clear identification of the data-use conditions. This enhances the metadata-level discovery without revealing any sensitive data.

Example

A pheno-clinical dataset from UNITO can be associated with DUO codes to specify usage restrictions, ensuring that external researchers know upfront whether data is available for non-commercial research or requires approval from a data access committee. This transparency encourages more convenient participation by data owners and data requestors.

1.5. Long-Term Sustainability and Reusability

Embedding licences and versioning information in the metadata ensures that HEREDITARY's datasets remain useful **beyond the project's lifetime**.

Icons made by Freepik, obtained from Flaticon

Example

A multi-modal dataset derived from UNIPD, published with a clear reuse licence and versioned records, allows future HEREDITARY researchers—or even external collaborators—to build upon the dataset, knowing its terms of use and how it evolved. This way, we ensure that the resources continue to provide value for years to come; and, if not, it is clear why.

How can the Task 3.6 team support your work?

We would love to hear your requirements, questions, comments or suggestions about the FAIRification proposals shown above. We are here to aid with your specific FAIRification needs.

If you want to **participate**, let us help you by:

- Contacting **Marcos Casado Barbero** (T3.6 Lead) (mcasado@ebi.ac.uk)
- Completing this brief [dataset contributor survey](#) (~5 minutes).²⁰

References

Icons used for the images in this document were obtained from Flaticon.com and made by Freepik.²¹

²⁰ <https://forms.gle/cLQuDixuqhck45Xd9>

²¹ <https://www.flaticon.com/authors/freepik>